

A Spectrophotometric Study of Cerium (IV)-3,5-Dinitrosalicylic Acid Complex

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The composition and stability of cerium (IV)-3, 5-dinitrosalicylic acid complex has been studied by spectrophotometric measurements. The reddish brown complex (λ max. = 500 m μ) has a 1 : 1 (metal : ligand) composition. The stability constant and free energy of formation of the complex at 30° were evaluated as 3.77 and -5.26 Kcals., respectively.

The complexes of trivalent metal ions like Fe, Al, Ga and In with 3,5-dinitrosalicylic acid (3, 5-DNS) have been studied spectrophotometrically.^{1,2} A close review of the literature, however, reveals the absence of any study on the system Ce-3, 5-DNS. The present note deals with the spectrophotometric study of the Ce-3, 5-DNS complex.

Anal-R (BDH) reagent ceric ammonium sulphate and Reidel's 3, 5-DNS were used. The solution of ceric ammonium sulphate was prepared by dissolving it in distilled water containing requisite amount of sulphuric acid.

Fig. 1.

Job's curves at 500 m μ . Concentrations of the reactants, Curve 1, M/300; Curve 2, M/400 and Curve 3, M/500.

1. C. Vassaliades, G. Manoussakis and G. Colovas, *Chim. Chronika* (Athens-Greece), 1964, 29 (12), 322.
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Absorbance measurements were carried out with Bauch and Lomb spectronic 20 colorimeter at 30°.

The method of Vosburgh and Cooper³ was employed for determining the nature of the chelate formed in solution. The most suitable absorbance lies at the wavelength 500 m μ .

The composition of the chelate was established by Job's continuous variation method⁴. Fig. 1 represents the Job's curves for the Ce-3, 5-DNS system at three different concentrations of the reactants and clearly indicates that cerium (IV) forms a 1 : 1 complex with 3, 5-DNS.

The stability constant of the complex was calculated from the Job's curves (Fig. 1) applying the formula,

$$K = \frac{x}{(a_1-x)(b_1-x)} = \frac{x}{(a_2-x)(b_2-x)} \quad \dots (1)$$

where a_1 , a_2 , b_1 and b_2 are the concentrations of the metal salt and 3, 5-DNS at two points on the two curves such that the optical density on them was the same. The value of stability constant was found to be 3.77. The free energy of formation of the complex was determined by using the expression

$$\Delta F^\circ = -RT \ln K \quad \dots (2)$$

where ΔF° is the standard free energy change, R the gas constant and T the absolute temperature. The value of ΔF° comes out to be -5.26 Kcals at 30°.

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